

FEATURES OF THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT OF LEAF-SHAPED BREAST TUMORS.

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Relevance. Fibroepithelial breast tumors are relatively rare in oncological practice. According to various authors, they make up from 0.3-2.6% of all mammary gland tumors, as a result of which this pathology is insufficiently studied. A leaf-shaped tumor (leaf-shaped fibroadenoma, giant myxomatous fibroadenoma, intracanalicular fibroadenoma with cell stroma, phylloid fibroadenoma, etc.) is a rather rare neoplasm, is of considerable interest for cytological study, but the small number of observations that researchers usually have does not allow solving most of the cardinal issues. The ability to relapse, malignancy with the development of breast sarcoma and distant metastasis are the main features of leaf-shaped tumors, in this connection, there are many questions concerning the etiology and pathogenesis of this nosological group. Given the rarity of these tumors, the peculiarities of the clinical course, the unreliability of diagnostic criteria, which complicates preoperative diagnosis. The study of the principles of surgical treatment seems to be very relevant, since surgical intervention is the main method of treating this pathology.

Material and method of research. The material for the study is a retrospective analysis of the medical histories of 28 patients with leaf-shaped breast tumors who were hospitalized in the surgical department of breast tumors on the basis of the Bukhara regional branch of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of oncology and radiology in the period from 2018-2021. The methods of examination are ultrasound, mammography, histological examination of the material, MRI.

Conclusions. The results of the scientific study show that with type I benign and phylloid fibroadenoma of the breast, the optimal treatment for both was tumor enucleation.

In case of pseudosarcomatous type II, the median of the postoperative relapse-free period was significantly better after the volume of the sectoral resection of the breast of a simple mastectomy, depending on the volume of the operation, the indicators of the relapse-free period were correspondingly better.

Type III sarcomatous type of tumor. With him, an operation was performed in the volume of a radical mastectomy. Phylloid fibroadenomas with sizes from 0.5 to 4 cm were enucleated, sectoral resection of tumors with sizes from 5 to 10 cm

and idle mastectomy with a tumor size of more than 10 cm was performed. The sarcomatous type should have a simple mastectomy, which in practice is not performed lymphodessection, because sarcomatous does not metastasize to regional lymph nodes.

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